

TEACHING AND LEARNING EXPERIENCES IN THE MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

This study is a qualitative research that aimed to propose recommendations to improve the implementation of modular distance learning delivery based on the experiences of Mathematics teachers and students. Data were collected through observation, survey, and interviews with 12 Junior High School Mathematics teachers and 48 Junior High School students from three high schools. The affinity diagram and content analysis were used to categorize and interpret the data. The findings revealed that Mathematics teachers faced challenges in coping with time, resources, communication, and health risks, but also created new opportunities to establish rapport with parents and learn the use of technology. Students experienced impediments in accessing, learning, and assessing with modules, but learned the value of time management and scheduling. The proposed recommendations were appropriate in addressing the impediments and challenges to improve the implementation of modular distance learning delivery. These recommendations focused on the preparation, distribution, and retrieval of modules, monitoring the learning process, and assessment of learning.

KEYWORDS: experiences; recommendation; improve; teaching; learning

I. INTRODUCTION COVID-19 has led to school closures globally and a shift to online and distance learning. This new approach poses challenges for educators and learners, but it has become necessary. "Education in Emergency" has been adopted through various learning platforms, even though they are not fully prepared. San Jose (2019) found that students enjoyed tutorials with visual aids and games but suggested improvements such as avoiding favoritism and long lectures. Harsasi and Sutawijaya (2018) found that course structure, tutorial flexibility, and technology quality affect student satisfaction in online tutorials. The study recommends paying attention to appearance quality, ease of use, and interaction between tutors and students. The present study considers experiences and recommendations for both printed and digital modular distance learning delivery.

II. METHODOLOGY This study used a qualitative method and descriptive research design to identify and describe the experiences of teachers and students in modular distance learning, including preparation, distribution, monitoring, and assessment. The design aimed to systematically describe their experiences and used various research methods, answering what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. The descriptive research design used a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables (McCombes, 2020). Further analysis of data through qualitative methods further established why it is that way or how it came to be (Cook & Richardt, 1979). Qualitative analysis explains why things happened and how they led to improvements in modular distance learning. Interviews with teachers and students, along with surveys and observations, helped understand their experiences, opinions, and behavior.

III. RESULT

Teachers' Positive Experiences

Teach Math with tech Easy online Math modules Connect with parents Effortless distribution of digital modules Smooth come-pick-go policy Build rapport with offline parents Collaborate with fellow teachers Innovate assessment methods Explore online Math apps.
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Teachers' Negative Experiences

Spending time on print module prep Lack of supplies Delayed digital module copies Overlapping tasks due to incomplete student work Health risks Late subject modules Difficulty tracing and labeling outputs Poor communication with students Difficulty giving feedback and validating learning
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Students' Positive Experiences

Accessing Math modules quickly and cost-effectively
Time management opportunities
Focus on teaching values over specific Math lessons
Ability to take Math exams at own pace through online platforms
Interest in learning through online Math assessment apps

Students' Negative Experiences

Incomplete print modules
Health risks from handling returned modules
No print modules when parents fail to claim them
No print modules due to teacher's schedule deviation
Difficulty understanding module lessons
Excessive tasks in the Math module
Poor communication with teachers
Too many activities and exercises in the module
Spending excessive time on module activities
Poor feedback on learning

III. DISCUSSION This study examines the positive and negative experiences of teachers during modular distance learning, which is similar to Abante (2021) et al.'s research on challenges in online and modular learning. Public and private school teachers face internet connectivity issues, limited resources, unresponsive parents, and a lack of training in online platforms and assessments. The challenges are similar regardless of school type. This study also aligns with Agarin's (2021) research on modular learning's impact on student academic behavior and performance, which found that it teaches time management skills and positively affects academic performance.

The recommendations in this study were carefully analyzed based on educational theories and experiences of teachers and are in line with Jokinen and Mikkonen's (2013) study on blended-learning-based adult nursing programs. The study found that teachers need knowledge of different pedagogical approaches and professional development to effectively plan and implement blended teaching and learning. These recommendations are vital for student learning: Designate personnel to check the completeness of modules before distribution; Adopt Come-Pick-Go Policy for module distribution and retrieval; Monitor teachers' adherence to the schedule for module distribution and retrieval; Organize a program for parents on the advantages of online modular distance learning; Intensify monitoring of learners' accomplishments and task submissions; Maintain follow-up and monitoring system enforced by advisers; The ICT Service of the DepEd Regional Office to provide digital copies of modules at least a week prior to the start of classes; Schools Division Offices to give materials for print modules immediately when the digital copy is available.

IV. CONCLUSION (1) Teachers faced challenges in modular distance learning delivery, including module preparation, distribution, and retrieval, monitoring the learning process, and assessment. These challenges impacted their time, resources, communication, and health. However, the situation also presented opportunities for teachers to connect with parents and improve their technical skills while adapting to the pandemic's difficulties. (2) Most experiences of the students were impediments to access to the modules, learning using the modules, and assessment of learning. However, students during these hard times learned the value of time management and scheduling. It taught the students values, not specific lessons. (3) The proposed recommendations, based on feedback from teachers and students, were appropriate in addressing challenges in implementing modular distance learning, including module preparation, distribution, retrieval, monitoring, and assessment.

IV. REFERENCES

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